

**Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins.
Part VII*. Synthesis of 4-Hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene[†] and
4-Hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2, 3-h) benzopyran**

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Claisen rearrangement of 4-methoxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxy-acetophenone gave 4-methoxy-6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-coumarin. This was cyclised to 4-methoxy-5',8-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydropsoalene by triturating with con. sulphuric acid. This dihydrofurocoumarin gave 4-methoxy-5',8-dimethyl-psoralene when refluxed with palladised charcoal in diphenyl ether; subsequent demethylation with hydrochloric acid gave 4-hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene. 4-Hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo(2,3-h) benzopyran was similarly synthesised by subjecting 4-methoxy-7-allyloxycoumarin to Claisen rearrangement, followed by cyclisation, dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal and demethylation with hydrochloric acid.

In recent years linear furocoumarins such as psoralene, xanthotoxin etc., have received attention on account of their therapeutic properties.^{1,2,3} It is also known that 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives are physiologically active⁴. It was therefore, thought of interest to synthesise 4-hydroxycoumarins having furan ring fused to the benzenoid part of the coumarin moiety. We report here the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IVb), 4-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (IXb) and ultraviolet spectra of (IVa) and (IVb) to study the relationship between structure and photodynamic activity of these compounds.

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (Ia) was allylated by refluxing it with allylbromide in acetone to 4-allyloxy-2-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (Ib). This was converted to 4-hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin (IIa) by heating it with sodium and ethyl carbonate according to Boyd and Robertson's method⁵. The methyl ether (IIb) was subjected to Claisen rearrangement by refluxing it in diethyl aniline to give 4-methoxy-6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-coumarin (IIc). This *o*-hydroxyallylcoumarin was cyclised to 4-methoxy-5',8-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydropsoalene (III) by triturating it with con. sulphuric acid. This method of cyclisation was found superior to earlier method⁶ which used hydrobromic acid or pyridine hydrochloride. This on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal

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† Nomenclature used in this paper is according to A. Curtius, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1959, **32**, 133

1. A. B. Lerner. *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1953, **20**, 299.
2. M. A. Pathak and J. H. Fellmann, *Nature*, London, 1960, **185**, 382.
3. M. A. Pathak, J. H. Fellmann and K. D. Kaufmann, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1960, **35**, 165.
4. M. A. Stahmann, C. F. Huebner and K. P. Link, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, **138**, 513.
5. Boyd and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 174.
6. L. Claisen and E. Tietse, *Ber.*, 1925, **58B**, 175.

afforded 4-methoxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IVa), which underwent demethylation to 4-hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IVb) when refluxed with con. hydrochloric acid. The U.V. Spectrum of (IVa) and (IVb) showed the characteristic bands at $326 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.93$) and $326 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.89$) thus indicating that the compounds are likely to be photodynamically active according to Pathak and Fellmann².

For the synthesis of compound (IXb), 4-allyloxy resacetophenone (Va) was converted to 4-hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (VIa) by heating with sodium and ethyl carbonate as before. The methyl ether of (VIa) on Claisen rearrangement in dimethyl aniline afforded 4-methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (VIb). This allylcoumarin was cyclised with con. sulphuric acid to 4-methoxy-8-methyl-8,9-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h)benzopyran (VII). This was also synthesised by another route. 3-Allylresacetophenone (Vb) was cyclised to 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-5-acetylcoumarin (VIII) by triturating with con. sulphuric acid. This was converted to (VII) by first reacting it with sodium and ethyl carbonate followed by methylation with dimethyl sulphate. (VII) was then dehydrogenated to (IXa) by refluxing it with palladised charcoal in diphenyl ether and demethylated to 4-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran (IXb) with con. hydrochloric acid as before.

These two furo-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives (IVb) and (IXb), on treatment with formaldehyde gave the corresponding methylene bis derivatives (X) and (XI).

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Allyloxy-2-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (Ib): A mixture of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (5.0 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) and allyl bromide (4.5 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on steam bath for 8 hr. After the evaporation of acetone the remaining solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was shaken

with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and separated sodium salt was filtered off. It was then acidified and extracted with ether. On evaporation of ether yellow colour liquid was obtained which was used for further reaction.

4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin (IIa): A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone (5.0 g.), diethyl carbonate (25 ml.) and pulverised sodium (4.0 g.) was heated on a water bath for 1 hr. Little alcohol was added to decompose unreacted sodium and then mixture was poured into water. The mixture was ether extracted and aqueous layer was acidified. The separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 215°. Yield 4 g. (Found : C, 66.74; H, 5.14%. C₁₃H₁₂O₄ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

Methyl ether of 4-hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin (IIb): Methyl ether was prepared as usual by using dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone, m.p. 173°. (Found : C, 68.54; H, 5.79%. C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.73%).

4-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylcoumarin (IIc): 4-Methoxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin (2 g.) was refluxed with diethyl aniline (6 ml.) on wire gauze for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool. The separated product was purified by treating it with dil. sodium hydroxide solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 218°. Yield 1 g. (Found : C, 68.10; H, 5.62%. C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.73%).

4-Methoxy-5',8-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydropsoralene (III): 4-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylcoumarin (0.8 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (3 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and water. The product was filtered off, washed with dil. sodium hydroxide solution, dried and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 198°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 68.27; H, 5.3%. C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.73%).

4-Methoxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IVa): 4-Methoxy-5',8-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydro-psoralene (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.3 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and allowed to cool. The separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 232°. Yield 0.2 g. $\lambda_{max}^{methanol}$ (log ϵ) 288 (3.12), 326 (3.93). (Found: C, 68.41; H, 5.39%. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.84; H, 4.95%).

4-Hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IVb): 4-Methoxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (0.2 g.) was dissolved in little alcohol (5 ml.) and was refluxed with con. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) for 45 min. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and separated product was then filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 305°. Yield 0.1 g. $\lambda_{max}^{chloroform}$ (log ϵ) 286 (4.06), 296 (4.09), 326 (3.89) (Found: C, 67.51; H, 4.19%. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.38%).

3,3'-Methylene bis-(4-hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene) (X): 4-Hydroxy-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (0.05 g.) was dissolved in ethyl alcohol (2 ml.) and was refluxed on a water bath with formaldehyde solution (0.5 ml.) for 30 min. The separated product was filtered hot and dried, m.p. above 320°. Yield 0.05 g. (Found: C, 68.68; H, 4.26%. $C_{27}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 68.64; H, 4.27%).

4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (VIa): A mixture of 4-allyloxy resacetophenone⁷ (5.0 g.), diethyl carbonate (25 ml.) and pulverised sodium (4.0 g.) was heated on a water bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 231°. Yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 65.99; H, 4.68%. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.05; H, 4.62%).

4-Methoxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (VIb): The methyl ether was prepared as usual by using dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 93°. Yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 67.66; H, 5.16%. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (VIc): 4-Methoxy-7-allyloxy coumarin (2.0 g.) was refluxed in dimethyl aniline (6 ml.) for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and separated product was filtered, treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 248°. Yield 1 g. (Found: C, 66.96; H, 5.28%. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-8-methyl-8,9-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (VII): 4-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-8-allylcoumarin (1 g.) was titrated with con. sulphuric acid (3 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was poured into ice. The separated product was worked up as before and the product crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 178°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 67.17; H, 5.30%. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

4-Methoxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (IXa): 4-Methoxy-8-methyl-8,9-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (0.6 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.4 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as

usual and the product crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 217°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 67.63; H, 4.45%. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.38%).

4-Hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (IXb) : 4-Methoxy-8-methyl-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran-2-one (0.3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (5 ml.) and then refluxed with con. hydrochloric acid (4 ml.) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water. The separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 310°. Yield 0.15 g. (Found : C, 66.28; H, 3.53%. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.73%).

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-hydroxy-5-acetylcoumaran (VIII) : 3-Allylresacetophenone⁷ (2 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice and water. The separated liquid was washed with water and then with petroleum ether (40–60°) and was used for further reaction.

4-Hydroxy-8-methyl-8,9-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran : Above thick liquid (2 g.) was dissolved in diethyl carbonate (10 ml.) and refluxed with pulverised sodium (1.5 g.) on water bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 278°. (Found : C, 65.87; H, 4.92%. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.05; H, 4.62%).

The above dihydrofurocoumarin (0.8 g.) was methylated by using dimethyl sulphate (0.7 ml.), acetone (50 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.). The product crystallised from dil. acetic acid. M.p. and mixed m.p. with 4-methoxy-8-methyl-8,9-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran as prepared earlier was not depressed.

3,3'-Methylene bis-(4-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran : 4-Hydroxy-8-methyl-2-oxo-2H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (0.05 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (3 ml.) and was refluxed with formaldehyde solution (0.5 ml.) on a water bath for 30 min. The separated product was filtered and dried, m.p. above 320°. Yield 0.05 g. (Found : C, 67.45; H, 3.50%. $C_{25}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 67.57; H, 3.63%).

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